

Chemical speciation and thermodynamic stability of quaternary mixed chelates of bio-metals involving lysine, proline and uracil

Divya Bartaria, V. P. Shukla and V. Krishna*

Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad, Allahabad-211 002, Uttar Pradesh, India

E-mail : vkrishna111@gmail.com

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Abstract : The metal-ligand formation constants of quaternary complexes of the type M_1M_2AB (where A = lysine/proline; B = uracil; $M_1 = M_2 = \text{Cu/Ni/Zn/Co}$) have been determined potentiometrically in biologically relevant conditions at constant ionic strength $I = 0.1 \text{ M NaNO}_3$. The overall stability constants have been evaluated using SCOGS computer program. The complexation equilibria have been derived on the basis of species distribution diagram. In all cases, amino acids and pyrimidines are found to be compatible ligands and thereby proving greater stability of ternary and quaternary complexes as compared to binary ones. The order of stability constants of quaternary systems with both the amino acids have been observed as : $\text{Cu-Ni} > \text{Cu-Zn} > \text{Cu-Co} > \text{Ni-Zn} > \text{Ni-Co} > \text{Co-Zn}$. The factors responsible for the compatibility of both the ligands have also been discussed.

Keywords : Uracil, proline, lysine, thermodynamic stability, chemical speciation.

Introduction

In continuation of our studies on mixed chelates of biological significance¹, we report herein the formation equilibria of multimetal-multiligand complexes, their overall stability constants and % distribution profiles in accordance with the pH variations. Aiming towards understanding the biochemical equilibria occurring in the biological system, present study involves lysine and proline as primary ligands, uracil as a secondary ligand and the transition metal ions Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} .

Quaternary complexes play important role in biological system² and such complexes are of significance in the study of bio-fluids particularly when hyper-accumulated metal ions are present for physiological or pathological nature³. Model studies with relatively simple molecules of known structure often yield valuable information that gives clues to the roles of metal ions in many enzymic reactions^{4,5}. In the present paper, the formation has been studied potentiometrically by Irving and Rossotti techniques⁶ at biologically relevant conditions.

Experimental

All the solutions were prepared in double distilled water. Potentiometric titrations of each ligand with standard carbonate free sodium hydroxide were carried out with an electric digital pH meter (Century-model CP901-

S) with a glass electrode at $37 \pm 1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $I = 0.1 \text{ M NaNO}_3$. Relatively low concentrations of metals and ligands are used. A stream of purified nitrogen was passed through the solutions throughout the titration. All the metal salts used were of AnalaR grade and were standardised volumetrically by titration with the disodium salt of EDTA in presence of suitable indicators, as described by Schwarzenbach⁷. For all the binary, ternary and quaternary systems, five solution mixture have been titrated against standardized NaOH (0.01 M) solution, keeping the total volume 50.0 ml in each case and the experimental details have been described elsewhere¹. Species distribution curves were obtained by plotting % concentration of the species obtained through SCOGS⁸, against pH.

Results and discussion

$M_1(\text{II})-M_2(\text{II})$ -lysine-uracil (1 : 1 : 1 : 1) systems :

It is clear from the species distribution diagram of $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}-\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}$ -lysine-uracil system (Fig. 1), that the mixed ligand species CuAB and NiAB show their maximum abundance at pH ~ 10.0 i.e. $\approx 7\%$ and $\approx 20\%$ respectively. The quaternary complex CuNiAB starts forming right from the beginning of titration showing the simultaneous process of complex formation. After a gradual increase, its concentration attains a maximum value ($\approx 85\%$) at pH ≈ 7.5 . The hydroxo species viz. $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})^+$ and $\text{Ni}(\text{OH})_2$

Fig. 1. Distribution curves of 1 : 1 : 1 : 1 Cu^{II}-Ni^{II}-lysine-uracil system : (1) AH₃, (2) AH₂, (3) AH, (4) BH, (5) Cu(OH)⁺, (6) Cu(OH)₂, (7) Ni(OH)⁺, (8) Ni(OH)₂, (9) CuA, (10) NiA, (11) CuB, (12) NiB, (13) CuAB, (14) NiAB, (15) CuNiAB.

have been taken into consideration, as the buffer region corresponding to metal ligand complex-formation equilibria has been found to be overlapping with the hydrolytic equilibria of M²⁺_(aq) metal ions. As is revealed from the speciation curves of Cu^{II}-Zn^{II}-lysine-uracil system, the ternary complex with Cu²⁺ is found to be remarkable species at relatively higher pH region showing stepwise formation of the complex, its maximum concentration being ≈65% at pH ≈ 10.0. Very small amount of ZnAB species may be observed within the pH range 8.7–10.0. There is a simultaneous process of formation of multimetal multiligand complex. A gradual incline in its concentration with the concomitant fall in the concentrations of protonated ligand species and free metal ions has been observed. At pH ≈7.5 its concentration is maximum i.e. 87%, thereafter a decrease has been observed which may be due to the appearance of hydroxo species Cu(OH)⁺ and Zn(OH)⁺.

The complex species identifiable in Cu^{II}-Co^{II}-lysine-uracil system are CuA, CoA, CoB, CuAB, CoAB and CuCoAB. Two types of ternary complex species are identifiable in the present system i.e. CuAB and CoAB, both formed at pH > 6.0. Quaternary complex Cu-Co-AB has been found to show its maxima ≈70% at pH ≈7.5 and beyond this pH, the gradual fall in its concentration may be attributed to the dissociation of the complex along

with the formation of hydroxo species. Co(OH)⁺ and Co(OH)₂ are the metal hydroxo species evidenced in the higher pH region.

It may be noticed that in Ni^{II}-Zn^{II}-lysine-uracil system also, NiA, NiB, NiAB, ZnAB and NiZnAB are the complex species assumed to prevail along with the hydroxo species Ni(OH)₂ and Zn(OH)₂. Similar trends and similar types of complex species have been revealed in Ni^{II}-Co^{II}-lysine-uracil and Zn^{II}-Co^{II}-lysine-uracil systems.

In most of the cases, the quaternary complex is formed simultaneously according to the equation :

However, in some cases discussed earlier, it is formed as per equation :

Dissociation of the quaternary complex and appearance of hydroxo species at higher pH region may be expressed as :

Other general hydrolytic equilibria are :

M₁(II)-M₂(II)-proline-uracil systems (1 : 1 : 1 : 1) :

In Cu^{II}-Ni^{II}-proline-uracil system (Fig. 2), mixed-ligand complex species CuAB and NiAB show their maximum presence at pH ≈10.5 i.e. ≈15% and ≈70% respectively. Thereafter, a decrease in concentration is observed due to the formation of hydroxo species. The quaternary complexation is simultaneous as it starts from the pH ≈3.1 and CuNiAB type of complex may be observed with its maximum abundance (≈95%) in the pH range ≈3.0–10.5. Two hydroxo species viz. Cu(OH)₂ and Ni(OH)⁺ have been assumed to prevail in the present system.

In Cu^{II}-Zn^{II}-proline-uracil system, the ternary complex CuAB is formed simultaneously in appreciable amount within the pH range 3.0–8.0 with a maxima at pH ≈ 5.6 (≈80%). On the other hand mixed ligand species ZnAB appreciably exists at some what higher pH range i.e. 5.8–8.0 attaining maximum value at pH ≈8.0 (i.e. ≈26%). The quaternary species CuZnAB is the most prevalent

Fig. 2. Distribution curves of 1 : 1 : 1 Cu^{II}-Ni^{II}-proline-uracil system : (1) AH₂, (2) AH, (3) BH, (4) Cu(OH)⁺, (5) Cu(OH)₂, (6) Ni(OH)⁺, (7) Ni(OH)₂, (8) CuA, (9) CuB, (10) NiA, (11) NiB, (12) CuAB, (13) NiAB, (14) CuNiAB

species formed as per general equilibrium mentioned further.

Among the species assumed in Cu^{II}-Co^{II}-proline-uracil system the binary, ternary and quaternary complexes show their remarkable presence in accordance with the general equilibria deduced further. Two types of ternary complex species have been examined in the present system i.e. CuAB and CoAB. The coordination of Cu²⁺ and Co²⁺ metal ions with both the ligand may be inferred on the basis of predominance of quaternary complex species being maximum ≈70% at pH ≈7.0. Its dissociation at still higher pH may be due to the formation of Cu(OH)₂ which is approximately 35% at pH ≈10.0.

In Ni^{II}-Zn^{II}-proline-uracil system, mixed ligand complexes NiAB and ZnAB have been identified along with the quaternary complex Ni-Zn-AB, whose concentration is maximum ≈70% at pH ≈9.3. Only one hydroxo species i.e. Ni(OH)₂ may be detected in the pH range ≈ 8.1-9.3.

In the same way, from the distribution profiles of Ni^{II}-Co^{II}-proline-uracil system, there is a rise in the concentration of mixed ligand complexes NiAB and CoAB with concomitant fall in the concentration of binary ones indicating stepwise formation of ternary complexes. The con-

centration of quaternary complex attains a maximum concentration ≈74% at pH ≈8.3. The hydroxo species identifiable are Ni(OH)₂ and Co(OH)⁺.

Among the common species assumed to prevail in Zn^{II}-Co^{II}-proline-uracil system, the ternary species existing in the pH range ≈7.7-10.5 are ZnAB and CoAB. The quaternary complex CoZnAB shows a usual incline in its concentration with the rise in pH attaining a maximum value ≈68% at pH ≈7.7. Only one hydroxo species Co(OH)₂ is found to exist in the pH range ≈8.1-9.5. The simultaneous process of quaternary complexation have been expressed as :

However, the step-wise formation of such quaternary complexes may be explained according to the following equations :

Conclusions :

From the SPE distribution curves it is concluded that in all the systems studied, there is simultaneous process of quaternary complexation in all the M₁(II)-M₂(II)-AB systems covering the entire pH region. However in case of Ni^{II}-Zn^{II}-proline-uracil system the formation of multimetal multiligand complex started at pH ≈5.2, in Ni^{II}-Co^{II}-proline-uracil system, at pH ≈4.6 and lastly in Zn^{II}-Co^{II}-proline-uracil system at pH ≈4.9.

The marked stabilization of the ternary relative to the binary complexes at higher pH and of the quaternary relative to the ternary ones at lower pH is reflected in the species distribution plots. The protonation constants of ligands, overall stability constants of binary, ternary and quaternary complexes determined have been compiled together and arranged in Tables 1 and 2 respectively. The stability constants of quaternary complexes in both types of systems have been found to fall in the following order : Cu-Ni > Cu-Zn > Cu-Co > Ni-Zn > Ni-Co > Co-Zn.

The lysine dianion offers to an incoming ligand both a functional group which is a potential hydrogen bond acceptor, the coordinated carboxylate oxygen and two primary amine groups which are potential hydrogen bond

Table 1. Stability constants and other related constants of binary, ternary and quaternary complexes of lysine (A) and uracil (B) with different metal ions in aqueous solution at 37 ± 1 °C, $I = 0.1$ M NaNO₃

(A)	Proton-ligand formation constants ($\log \beta_{000r0t}$)						
	AH ₃	21.84					
	AH ₂	19.77					
	AH	10.69					
	BH	9.47					
(B)	Hydrolytic constants ($\log \beta_{p000t}/\log \beta_{0q00t}$)						
		Cu	Ni	Zn	Co		
	M(OH) ⁺	-6.29	-8.10	-7.89	-8.23		
	M(OH) ₂	-13.10	-16.87	-14.92	-17.83		
(C)	Metal-ligand constants ($\log \beta_{p0r00}/\log \beta_{0qr00}/\log \beta_{p00s0}/\log \beta_{0q0s0}$) : Binary systems						
		Cu	Ni	Zn	Co		
	MA	11.56	8.30	8.22	6.12		
	MB	8.25	6.80	6.61	6.28		
(D)	Metal-ligand constants ($\log \beta_{p0rs0}/\log \beta_{0qrs0}$) : Ternary systems						
		Cu	Ni	Zn	Co		
	MAB	15.54	12.64	11.24	11.63		
(E)	Metal-ligand constants ($\log \beta_{pqrs0}$) : Quaternary systems						
		Cu-Ni	Cu-Zn	Cu-Co	Ni-Zn	Ni-Co	Zn-Co
	M ₁ -M ₂ -AB	23.40	23.28	22.25	21.55	19.15	18.85

Table 2. Stability constants and other related constants of binary, ternary and quaternary complexes of proline (A) and uracil (B) with different metal ions in aqueous solution at 37 ± 1 °C, $I = 0.1$ M NaNO₃

(A)	Proton-ligand formation constants ($\log \beta_{000r0t}$)						
	AH ₂	12.79					
	AH	9.37					
	BH	9.47					
(B)	Hydrolytic constants ($\log \beta_{p000t}/\log \beta_{0q00t}$)						
		Cu	Ni	Zn	Co		
	M(OH) ⁺	-6.29	-8.10	-7.89	-8.23		
	M(OH) ₂	-13.10	-16.87	-14.92	-17.83		
(C)	Metal-ligand constants ($\log \beta_{p0r00}/\log \beta_{0qr00}/\log \beta_{p00s0}/\log \beta_{0q0s0}$) : Binary systems						
		Cu	Ni	Zn	Co		
	MA	8.04	6.39	5.60	5.83		
	MB	8.25	6.80	6.61	6.28		
(D)	Metal-ligand constants ($\log \beta_{p0rs0}/\log \beta_{0qrs0}$) : Ternary system						
		Cu	Ni	Zn	Co		
	MAB	16.51	11.66	11.40	11.54		
(E)	Metal-ligand constants ($\log \beta_{pqrs0}$) : Quaternary system						
		Cu-Ni	Cu-Zn	Cu-Co	Ni-Zn	Zn-Co	Zn-Co
	M ₁ -M ₂ -AB	23.35	23.15	22.84	19.68	19.15	19.61

donor. Thus lysine is a potentially tridentate ligand. The side ϵ -NH₂ group of the lysine residue in peptides and proteins is one of the potential donor sites for metals especially copper ion complexation. However its coordination to the metal centre generally involves the forma-

tion of unusually large chelate rings. This fact, together with its high pK value, makes ϵ -NH₂-Cu^{II} bond formation unfavorable at neutral or acidic pH⁹. The same is true for lysine itself¹⁰. On the other hand, in the alkaline pH range, metal ions become more competitive with res-

pect to protons. ϵ -NH₂ coordination in binuclear complexes of Cu^{II} and oligopeptides has been reported, both in solution¹¹ and in the solid state¹². The most basic group is the ϵ -amino group of the lysine. The terminal amino group is less basic than the ϵ -amino group of the lysine residue, due to the proximity of the electron-withdrawing carbonyl group of the peptide bond. Fully protonated form of ligand proline (A⁻) is represented by H₂A⁺. It usually functions as bidentate ligand using one carboxyl and one imino group for coordination. Proline has one replaceable proton and behaves as monobasic acid.

Protonation constants for the ligands have been determined by Irving-Rossotti titration technique¹³ and are presented in Tables 1 and 2. Values of protonation constants are in fair agreement with the values reported in literature¹⁴. In Ni^{II}, Co^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes uracil¹⁵ acts as a monodentate ligand coordinating through only one nitrogen, but in the Cu^{II} complex, it behaves as bidentate ligand coordinating through carbonyl oxygen and nitrogen. Threshold collision – Induced Dissociation and theoretical studies¹⁶ find that the preferred binding site for the alkali cations to uracil is at O4. It was found that the alternate binding site at O2 is higher in energy by 14.4 kJ/mol for Li⁺, 11.7 kJ/mol for Na⁺ and 11.6 kJ/mol for K⁺. Thus, on an analogy, it would be reasonable to assume that in present complexes, N3 and O4 of the carbonyl group are the binding sites for chelation to occur.

On the basis of electrostatic considerations, it can be seen that ligand A reacts first with the bivalent metal ion to form M(II)-A species. The interaction of the incoming secondary ligand B with M(II)-A is energetically favourable as compared to the interactions between [M(H₂O)_n]²⁺ and B. Hence, the stability of the mixed ligand complex is enhanced considerably. These facts indicate that ligands A and B are compatible ligands in the coordination sphere of the bivalent metal ion. According to Fridman¹⁷, if two ligands are compatible in the coordination sphere of the metal ion, the ternary complex and quaternary complex formed will be more stable than either of the parent complexes. Sakurai *et al.*¹⁸ carried out extensive studies to establish the laws governing interactions of this nature. In the present case, these factors also appear to contribute to the elevation of the stability of ternary and quaternary complexes.

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